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ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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HOME

The grass is turning brown again.
A velvet mat sprawling beneath the summer breath,
The rain flowers, wrapped in gentle breeze,
Sway gaily as they welcome the summer days.
And they welcome me.

Across the street, a stone-throw away,
The sea with tiny ripple,
Are shimmering against the morning sun.
They too, welcome me.

The leaves are turning brown again.
They drop to the clay-caked earth,
Piling a heap of pleasant memories
Of home not so far away.
Such memories welcome me.

Amidst shouts of peddlers, cries of babies,
Screeches of wheels and blows of horns,
A deafening noise creeping its way out
From crammed small huts, from darkness,
And gloom. T'was home.

And now the trees are crowned green.
And rain flowers are not alone in bloom.
The mountain of hope and the highway
Of memories meet and find their way
To a new-found home.

When December wind chills my soul,
When blooming flowers are no more,
When the grass turns brown and the leaves
Loke days, fall one by one,
My memories, my thoughts, my very breath
Will find me H O M E.